

humantech

D3.4 – Domain-adapted synthetic dataset for 3D semantic segmentation

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D3.4 - Domain-adapted synthetic dataset for 3D semantic segmentation

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
PCS	Point cloud segmentation
IoU	Intersection over union metrics
mIoU	Mean IoU over object category class
Acc	Accuracy metrics
mAcc	Mean accuracy over object category class
BIM	Building information modelling
CAD	Computer-aided design
IFC	A specific file format used for BIM models
RGB	Red, Green, and Blue values for any give colour
UE5	Unreal Engine 5
FOV	Field of view
DOF	Depth of field
UDA	Unsupervised domain adaptation
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
UGV	Unmanned ground vehicle

Abstract

In this report, we review the benefits of artificial data in semantic point cloud segmentation to improve segmentation on real-life data. This could also be a response to the lack of annotated data on some fields, and more especially for BIM models. Annotating data by hand is a very tedious task and has to be supervised in some ways. The main point of focus is 3D interiors scans obtained with a LiDAR sensor. Our work will be divided into two main parts. The first part targets artificial data generation using a simulated LiDAR sensor inside Unreal Engine 5. There is a need to have more annotated data and generating artificial datasets will be proven to be a viable alternative. Our reference will be the Stanford dataset which consists of real-world interior scans (alongside their annotations, meshes, semantics, surface normal, materials and textures). The second part consists in the evaluation of such artificially generated data. In order to measure the benefits of using artificial data, we will use domain adaptation and finetuning on two pretrained models for semantic segmentation. We will also discuss the need of “good” artificial data, especially when it comes to complex tasks – even regardless of the model, and methods to generate them.

The HumanTech project

The European construction industry faces three major challenges: increase the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improve its productivity, and become greener, making efficient use of resources.

To address these challenges, HumanTech proposes to develop **human-centred cutting-edge technologies** such as wearables for workers' safety and support and robots that can harmoniously coexist with human workers while contributing to the ecological transition of the sector.

HumanTech aims to achieve major advances in cutting-edge technologies that will enable a safe, rewarding, and digital work environment for a new generation of highly skilled construction workers and engineers.

These advances will include:

- **Robotic devices equipped with vision and intelligence** that allow them to navigate autonomously and safely in highly unstructured environments, collaborate with humans and dynamically update a semantic digital twin of the construction site in which they are.
- **Smart, unobtrusive workers protection and support equipment.** From exoskeletons activated by body sensors for posture and strain to wearable cameras and XR glasses that provide real-time workers' location and guidance for them to perform their tasks efficiently and accurately.
- An entirely new breed of **Dynamic Semantic Digital Twins (DSDTs) of construction sites** that simulate in detail the current state of a construction site at the geometric and semantic level, based on an extended Building Information Modelling (BIM) formulation that contains all relevant structural and semantic dimensions (BIMxD). BIMxDs will act as a common reference for all human workers, engineers, and autonomous machines.

The **HumanTech consortium** is formed by 22 organisations — leading research institutes and universities, innovative hi-tech SMEs, and large enterprises, construction groups and a construction SME representative — from 10 countries, bringing expertise in 11 different disciplines. The consortium is led by the German Research Center for Artificial Intelligence's Augmented Vision department.

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1. Introduction

The utilization of annotated data serves as a foundational requirement for training networks in semantic segmentation tasks on authentic data scans. However, an alternative methodology exists: leveraging artificially generated scans equipped with annotations. This obviates the necessity for manual semantic labelling of objects, as depicted in Figure 1. Such an approach necessitates the emulation of authentic sensor behaviour within a virtual environment, underscoring imperatives such as scalability, reproducibility, and computational prowess.

The generation of computer-simulated models that faithfully replicate real-world scenes is pivotal for crafting simulated point clouds. Nevertheless, this endeavor is fraught with significant considerations:

1. **Establishment of Inter-item Rules:** To engender artificial scenes that exhibit plausible configurations, it becomes imperative to delineate rules or inferential relationships among constituent elements.
2. **Multiplicity of Models:** A vast repertoire of distinct models, each accompanied by a set of valid and acceptable poses and spatial arrangements within scenes, is indispensable.
3. **Specialized Object Modeling:** Within domains like HumanTech, certain construction-centric entities, e.g., scaffolding, remain conspicuously absent from open-source repositories. Consequently, there's an imperative to meticulously model these intricate 3D objects.
4. **Enhancing Realism:** The fidelity and realism inherent to generated data are instrumental in bridging the sim-to-real divide, thereby catalyzing the efficacy of subsequent downstream algorithms.

Within the HumanTech context, it's assumed that BIMxD models are accessible, from the T3.6 Scan-to-BIM pipeline, showcasing real construction sites in true scale. These models contain structural and building components, enabling the creation of artificial point clouds enriched with semantics. These synthetic 3D data can then be employed to train T3.5 segmentation algorithms effectively, through domain adaptation and/or transfer learning. Domain adaptation and transfer learning are essential in machine and deep learning, leveraging insights from one domain to improve outcomes in related areas. Domain adaptation fine-tunes models from one domain to excel in another, while transfer learning applies expertise from one task to enhance performance in a related

task. Both methods address data limitations, reduce training costs, and boost model effectiveness across diverse applications.

Figure 1 – example of manually annotated panoramic image using Coco Annotator¹. This tool works by allowing the user to create closed shapes to define boundaries, which will be used to compute the ground truth when the final dataset will be fed to a model.

In Section 2, we outline the methodology for data generation, followed by a detailed dataset description in Section 3. Sections 4 and 5 delve into fine-tuning and domain adaptation techniques, respectively. We wrap up with our conclusions in Section 6.

¹ <https://github.com/jsbroks/coco-annotator>

2. Data generation methodology

2.1. Overview

Considering the aforementioned constraints highlighted in Section 1, our focus pivots towards generating point clouds utilizing Building Information Modeling (BIM) models specific to construction sites. Building Information Modeling, commonly abbreviated as BIM, encapsulates the digital representation methodology employed to capture both the functional and physical attributes of buildings or locations. Within the BIM domain, the term "BIM file format" encompasses a spectrum of data file formats germane to the sector. Notably, the buildingSMART² alliance pioneered the creation of the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) data file format³—a universally acknowledged and predominant BIM file format.

Within the HumanTech framework, it is presumed that inputs for the BIM models emanate either from domain experts employing BIM creation tools such as Autodesk⁴ or are derived from the T3.6 Scan-to-BIM pipeline integral to the HumanTech ecosystem.

Figure 2 – A BIM model inside Blender (3.6.2) with the BlenderBIM (0.0.230701) addon [2]. In this image, we have loaded a BIM model inside Blender. A wall is selected, and its tag is visible in the top left corner. This BIM model represents a set of rooms in a hospital. This model includes one floor (or slab), multiple walls, windows and columns (we can see one column going through the ceiling and the upper level in the middle of the screen).

² <https://www.buildingsmart.de/>

³ <https://www.buildingsmart.org/standards/bsi-standards/industry-foundation-classes/>

⁴ <https://www.autodesk.com/solutions/aec/bim>

BIM models offer enhanced flexibility and a diverse range of valuable information compared to traditional Computer-Aided Design (CAD). They encompass detailed specifications for movable objects and can incorporate multiple layers to construct intricate objects. Doors, as an example, epitomize this versatility, presenting options such as rotation axes or considerations for sliding and draggable functionalities. Additionally, traversable layers, like those representing transparent materials, enable the depiction of scenes where movement through the environment and activation/relocation of objects within a BIM model are feasible.

It is imperative for our segmentation models and generated point clouds to acknowledge these nuances to effectively mimic or interpret realistic data. Figure 2 provides a visual representation of a BIM model generated in T3.6, utilizing 3D scans acquired from handheld, unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), and unmanned ground vehicle (UGV) devices during the data acquisition process within the HumanTech framework.

2.2. Tools

To emulate sensors that align with the authentic physical principles of real-world sensors, we employ an Unreal Engine 5 plugin [1] from RPTU Robotics Research Lab. Within this framework, BIM models facilitate the generation of standard materials and meshes compatible with UE5. During the scanning procedure, the LiDAR sensor necessitates manual positioning and movement throughout the virtual environment. As it traverses the scene, the LiDAR sensor accumulates data on hit-points, subsequently storing this information in a designated file.

Optimizing ray tracing efficiency, the plugin harnesses GPU resources to enhance performance. The resultant dataset comprises the object instance ID that the LiDAR ray intersected with, coupled with three-dimensional XYZ coordinates and an RGB coloration for each point. Given the inherent limitations of the LiDAR sensor's field of view, both horizontally and vertically, it becomes imperative to execute multiple scans. This iterative approach ensures the attainment of the requisite accuracy and density of scans necessary for comprehensive data representation.

Specification	Details
Number of channels	64
Range (in meters)	120
Number of points per seconds	2.2 million
Horizontal FOV (in degrees)	360
Vertical FOV (in degrees)	26.9
Angular resolution (in degrees, azimuth)	0.08
Accuracy (in cm)	< 2
Vertical resolution (in degrees)	0.4

Table 1 – specifications of the LiDAR sensor we are simulating in Unreal Engine 5 [4]. The number of channels, the range, the horizontal and vertical FOV, as well as angular resolution, accuracy and vertical resolution are the same in our simulation in Unreal Engine 5 [4]. The only downside is that the number of points per second is tied to the performance of the machine the simulation is running on. However, this does not make any difference since we are scanning static scenes.

Table 1 delineates the specifications of the Velodyne HDL64E-S3 [3] LiDAR sensor employed in conjunction with Unreal Engine 5 [4]. A pivotal parameter is the actual count of laser beams or channels, typically ranging between 8 and 128. This channel count significantly influences the sensor's resolution; a higher channel count invariably yields enhanced resolution capabilities.

The sensor's operational range determines its capability to detect objects within a specified distance. A reduced number of rays might result in fewer intersections with objects within that range. The maximum recording capacity is quantified in points per second. To ascertain the registration frequency of each laser beam, this metric is divided by the number of channels. Naturally, a broader operational range would correspond to a diminished points-per-second output.

Furthermore, the LiDAR sensor's horizontal field of view (FOV) quantifies its scanning breadth along the horizontal axis. For reference, the human eye possesses an approximate horizontal FOV of 135 degrees. Analogously, the vertical FOV characterizes the scanning capability along the y-axis, with the human eye typically encompassing slightly over 180 degrees.

Figure 3 – simplified view of the effect of different angular resolution for LiDAR sensors. To the left, a high angular resolution allows for better distinction in almost all circumstances. To the right, distinct objects may be overlapping in the sensor's view. Activated receptors are coloured in yellow.

The angular resolution of a LiDAR sensor is inherently tied to the density of points or pixels within a given unit area. This metric delineates the angular separation between consecutive laser casts, serving as a crucial indicator of the sensor's efficacy in discerning closely situated features or objects within the horizontal plane. Notably, as depicted in Figure 3, finer details become discernible as the angular resolution diminishes.

Furthermore, when assessing the depth accuracy of a point cloud, it's essential to recognize its inherent limitations. The most pronounced inaccuracies typically manifest in the depth dimension. Concurrently, the sensor's capability to differentiate between objects or surfaces spanning varying elevations is encapsulated by the term "vertical resolution."

2.3. Limitations

Each LiDAR ray produces a dataset of hit-points, indicating whether the ray intersected with a UE5 mesh or encountered an empty space within its designated field of view. Alongside capturing 3D coordinates for these hits, the LiDAR also logs an RGB color value corresponding to successful intersections. However, it's crucial to note that this recorded

color does not necessarily align with the material or texture characteristics of the intercepted object.

Moreover, even if BIM models incorporated richer color data beyond mere RGB fields, the color representation would remain inaccurate. Essentially, the recorded color reflects the object's appearance relative to external lighting conditions. Consequently, when the LiDAR operates in environments devoid of external illumination, such as a completely dark room, all detected objects would appear uniformly dark.

This poses challenges, especially within the UE5 framework, where emissive objects in BIM models do not emit light. The nuances of reflection and diffusion are also overlooked in this simplified representation. Consequently, the resulting RGB renderings may not faithfully replicate real-world scenarios, potentially leading to discrepancies when juxtaposed with genuine point clouds and diverse applications.

The integration of the LiDAR sensor plugin with Unreal Engine presents several challenges, primarily stemming from the engine's handling of blueprints and BIM models. Notably, Unreal Engine 5 encounters difficulties in correctly processing ".ifc" files and BIM models. Although the engine retains IFC tags during the import process—such as "IFCSlab," "IFCDoors," and the like—it fails to preserve individual IDs. These IDs, uniquely assigned by Blender during BIM model exports, are crucial for accurate model representation.

A potential solution to circumvent this issue involves a strategic approach: one could extract object IDs while concurrently importing the associated IFC tags. By maintaining a localized database that correlates these IDs with their respective IFC tags, a more accurate representation within the Unreal Engine ecosystem can be achieved. These IFC tags, generated through tools like ifcopenshell [5], offer a structured method for embedding metadata directly within the BIM model, facilitating more coherent data interpretation and utilization.

3. Synthetic Dataset

Figure 4 showcases our generated dataset, depicting synthetic expansive indoor environments crafted from BIM models. This dataset includes the “.ifc” file, which stands as a representation of the specific BIM model employed for simulating lidar point clouds within the Unreal Engine simulator. Additionally, the dataset contains an “.npy” file that encapsulates the 3D xyz coordinates (measured in centimetres), RGB color values, category IDs corresponding to the objects, refer Table 2, and their distinct instance IDs associated with each 3D point. Our dataset is made public and can be downloaded using this [link](#). The dataset comprises the DFKI office room and Weingarten hospital room scenarios used across the WP3.

Figure 4 (a): BIM model of DFKI office floor obtained manually and/or from T3.6 scan-to-bim pipeline, (b): Synthetic RGB point cloud generated using aforementioned BIM model in UnrealEngine5, (c) and (d): Object instances and semantics ground truth annotations for generated synthetic scan.

IFC Tag	Object Category
IfcWall	Wall
IfcBeam	Beam
IfcColumn	Column
IfcDoor	Door
IfcWindow	Window
IfcSlab	Floor
IfcCurtainWall	CurtainWall
IfcDuctSegment	Pipe
IfcDuctFittings	Pipe Fitting
IfcStair	Stair
IfcRailing	Stair Railing
IfcPlate	Curtain Panel

Table 2 – Details of simulated BIM IFC object in our experiments and corresponding object category mapped based on the ontology-based semantic annotations guidelines [14].

Table 2 systematically categorizes various BIM IFC objects and aligns them with their respective object categories. This categorization ensures clarity and standardization in understanding the type and function of each BIM component. Using ontology-based semantic annotation guidelines as a foundation ensures that these classifications are grounded in established industry standards and definitions.

Area	# Floor(s)	# Room(s)	# Point(s)
DFKI Office	1	1	5.2 million
Weingarten A	2	20 + 19	30.9 + 31.9 million
Weingarten B	1	12	21.9 million
Weingarten C	1	11	18.3 million

Table 3 – Details of our synthetic data generated from different corresponding BIM models.

Figure 5 – Visualization of our synthetic data object instances.

On the other hand, Table 3 delves into the specifics of synthetic data derived from diverse BIM models. It offers a breakdown of different areas within these models, providing insights into the number of floors, rooms, and the corresponding point counts. Such detailed metrics are essential for evaluating the scale, complexity, and intricacies of each model. By presenting this information, stakeholders can gain a comprehensive understanding of the synthetic data's scope and its relevance in various applications or experiments.

4. Fine Tuning

4.1. Overview

In the realm of deep learning, fine-tuning stands as a critical facet of transfer learning, allowing adjustments to a pre-trained model's parameters for optimized performance on a specific task using a specialized dataset. This method capitalizes on the pre-trained model's ability to extract relevant features, necessitating selective weight modifications rather than extensive retraining. Key advantages of fine-tuning include enhanced task-specific performance, efficiency over starting from scratch due to leveraging pre-existing features, and the ability to customize the model for specific domains or applications, ensuring alignment with unique requirements and nuances.

The application of pretrained backbones, coupled with fine-tuning, has demonstrated efficacy across various domains, including 2D vision and natural language processing. Such an approach often surpasses the performance of networks designed for specific tasks. In alignment with this trend, Swin3D [6] introduces an innovative backbone model tailored for 3D indoor scene comprehension tasks, capitalizing on extensive pretraining data.

To navigate the substantial computational demands inherent in this domain, the methodology integrates sparse voxel techniques for representing the 3D point cloud of the input scene. Leveraging the advantages of the pretrained synthetic data backbone, the system undergoes a meticulous two-step fine-tuning regimen, ultimately achieving benchmark results in semantic segmentation tasks⁵.

⁵ <https://paperswithcode.com/paper/swin3d-a-pretrained-transformer-backbone-for>

4.2. Results

Class	IoU ⁶	Accuracy
Beam	0.9554	0.9690
Board	0.9808	0.9862
Bookcase	0.8809	0.9699
Chair	0.4557	0.5040
Clutter	0.6548	0.6635
Column	0.7885	0.9451
Door	0.8571	0.9183
Floor	0.9128	0.9783
Sofa	0.8475	0.8875
Table	0.8176	0.9049
Wall	0.8463	0.8670
Window	0.6788	0.7873

Table 4 – Segmentation results of Swin3D network [6] trained on Structured3D synthetic dataset [7] and finetuned + evaluated on Stanford real-world dataset [9].

Upon pretraining on large scale Structured3D synthetic data [7] followed by fine-tuning and evaluation using the Stanford dataset [9], Swin3D exhibits commendable performance across all specified classes. As delineated in Table 4 and Figure 6, it is noteworthy to highlight a particular dataset characteristic: given the architectural design where the ceiling of one room essentially serves as the floor for the room situated above it, the Stanford dataset notably lacks explicit ceiling data entries.

⁶ Intersection over Union (IoU) is a metric from 0 to 1 that specifies the amount of overlap between the predicted and ground truth.

Figure 6 – Visualization of (a): ground truth object semantics from Stanford real-world dataset [9], (b): corresponding output from Swin3D network [6]. The point clouds are coloured w.r.t their corresponding object instances.

Class	IoU	Accuracy
Wall	0.6116	0.8111
Floor	0.0029	0.0029

Table 5 – Segmentation results of Swin3D network [6] trained on Structured3D synthetic dataset [7] and finetuned + evaluated on our synthetic dataset.

The results presented in Table 5 and Figure 7 showcase promising outcomes when evaluated on our synthetic dataset, particularly for well-represented classes. However, it's crucial to acknowledge a limitation in the dataset generation process using UE5—automation is not yet at an optimal level. Consequently, the available dataset comprises a constrained number of rooms and scenes. While this limitation inevitably influences the results, the ability to distinguish between the floor and the walls stands out as a positive sign of promise in the current context. Despite the existing constraints, the preliminary findings suggest encouraging prospects for further refinement and expansion of the dataset.

Figure 7 – Visualization of (a): ground truth object semantics from our synthetic dataset, (b): corresponding output from Swin3D network [6]. The point clouds are coloured w.r.t their corresponding object instances.

5. Domain Adaptation

5.1. Overview

Domain adaptation [12] enhances a model's adaptability to diverse datasets by aligning inherent distributions across domains. Key methodologies include feature extraction, which prioritizes resilient attributes like object morphology and chromaticity; data augmentation, which expands the training dataset for improved generalization; and the use of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) [11], specialized in generating synthetic datasets that enrich the model's training capabilities for the target domain.

In this segment, we examine DODA [8], a sophisticated data-centric Sim-to-Real domain adaptation framework designed explicitly for 3D semantic segmentation. The conventional approach of training on synthetic datasets and subsequently applying the model to real-world environments is plagued by significant domain discrepancies. Specifically, simulated environments tend to feature pristine objects and unblemished surfaces. Conversely, real-world environments inherently introduce challenges such as occlusions and noise patterns when reconstructing point clouds from RGB-D inputs.

To address these inherent domain disparities, the researchers devised a bifurcated pipeline comprising a pre-training phase followed by a self-training phase. This innovative approach culminated in a comprehensive unsupervised domain adaptation framework tailored for 3D indoor semantic segmentation. The DODA architecture integrates virtual scan simulations to emulate authentic point cloud patterns from real-world scenarios. Furthermore, the inclusion of tail-aware cuboid mixing serves to mitigate context discrepancies by establishing a cuboid-centric intermediary domain.

Empirical evaluations elucidate the efficacy of the DODA framework. Notably, DODA achieves performance enhancements of 22% and 19% in terms of mIoU when benchmarked against the source-only model across transitions from 3D-FRONT [10] to ScanNet [13] and 3D-FRONT [10] to Stanford [9], respectively.

5.2. Results

Class	IoU	Accuracy
Wall	0.9060	0.9909
Floor	0.9741	0.9747
Door	0.1769	0.1769
Ceiling	0.9101	0.9352

Table 6 – Segmentation results of DODA [8] network trained on 3DFront synthetic dataset [10] and evaluated on Stanford real-world dataset [9].

Table 6 and Figure 8 collectively illustrate that DODA has achieved commendable performance in unsupervised domain adaptation, particularly regarding mean IoU (mIoU) and mean Accuracy (mAcc), when transitioning from 3D-Front [10] to Stanford [9]. Notably, notable success is observed for object categories such as wall, floor, and ceiling.

However, the efficacy of the DODA method in handling column and beam categories on the Stanford dataset is not as evident. This discrepancy in performance may be attributed to substantial disparities in data patterns across the domains, highlighting potential challenges in adapting the model to certain structural elements.

Figure 8 –Visualization of (a): ground truth object semantics from Stanford real-world dataset [9], (b): corresponding output from DODA [8] network. The point clouds are coloured w.r.t their corresponding object instances.

6. Conclusion

In this comprehensive report, we delved into the generation of artificial datasets leveraging Unreal Engine 5 with real BIM models and obtained 3D synthetic point cloud dataset with semantic and instance annotations. A paramount focus of the project was achieving realism in LiDAR modelling within UE5. The development of tools to address technical challenges, often arising from software incompatibilities, significantly influenced the extensive testing and customization of various networks and models.

Despite the strides made, the generation of artificial scenes reveals areas for improvement, as highlighted in section 5. Emphasizing the importance of data quality becomes imperative, particularly when the predominant efforts are directed toward enhancing model quality. Realistic rendering and optimized sensor placements are critical to capturing the entire scene with an optimal number of points, thereby avoiding the creation of unwieldy datasets. The RGB output also requires refinement to meet the standards observed in datasets like Structured3D [7] and 3D-Front [10]. Additionally, the current generation method falls short in providing information on the normals of various planes within the scene, a data facet that holds relevance for computational purposes, considering reference datasets incorporate this information.

On the front of semantic segmentation, superior results were achieved through fine-tuning on reference datasets. The next frontier involves improving domain adaptation from our synthetic data to real data. However, the crux lies in acquiring more data to ensure consistent and analyzable results. A critical challenge arises in aligning point clouds in real-world scenarios. Given that each scene comprises multiple point clouds, ensuring their alignment for processing is a substantial concern that warrants concerted attention.

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